

SUSTAINABLE STRAW POTENTIAL IN SWEDEN – A CASE STUDY TO SUPPLY STRAW FOR ETHANOL PRODUCTION

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ABSTRACT: When agriculture is to supply a growing bioeconomy with biomass, straw has been identified as one of residues with the largest potential. As removal of straw from fields will have a negative impact on soil humus development compared with straw incorporation it is important to make sure that a system including straw removal does not negatively effect the long-term soil fertility. As part of the EU-financed project AGROinLOG a Swedish demonstration case was made to supply 80,000 tonnes of winter wheat straw annually to 2nd generation bioethanol production. The straw removal from the case study area of Norrköping and surrounding counties, in the south-eastern part of Sweden, was evaluated from a soil fertility aspect using a model that estimates the sustainability of a cropping system regarding soil fertility and yield levels based on humus content, climate and soil type. The assessment revealed the possibility to remove 230,000 tonnes of winter wheat straw from the surrounding counties of Norrköping without reaching the humus limit. The margin to 80,000 tonnes is large and collecting this amount of winter wheat straw annually may well be possible.

Keywords: agricultural residues, wheat straw, soil fertility, biobased economy, second generation ethanol, lignocellulose.

1 BACKGROUND

Agriculture will play an important role in the transition to a sustainable, fossil free society and straw has been identified as one of residues with the largest potential. At the same time, straw is already partly utilized in the animal production for feed and bedding. Furthermore, effects on soil fertility is increasingly important when agriculture is going to supply a growing bioeconomy with biomass.

The result presented here estimates the sustainable straw potential for a demonstration case to supply 80,000 tonnes of winter wheat straw annually to the ethanol plant of Lantmännen Agroetanol in Norrköping, Sweden, see Figure 1. The work is part of the EU-project AGROinLOG that deals with utilization of non-used resources and residues to create new business lines and products at agro-industries, taking advantage of their variations in seasonal operation. In the Swedish demonstration case, straw-based second-generation ethanol production will be enhanced by improved logistics and better utilization of the lignin residue remaining after ethanol production.

Figure 1: Location of the case study ethanol plant owned by Lantmännen Agroetanol in Norrköping, Sweden.

Straw can be obtained from cereal and oilseed crops. Wheat and barley are the most common cereal crops, occupying 40% and 35%, respectively, of the total cereal acreage in Sweden.

Overall soil humus content in arable land in Sweden is estimated to be increasing at present. This is partly explained by a growing number of horses in recent decades, which has resulted in an increase in the proportion of ley in many crop rotations. However, there are differences between areas, with e.g. a decline in soil humus content in parts of southern Sweden [1].

All removal of straw from fields will have a negative impact on soil humus development compared with straw incorporation. However, arable land in Sweden is dominated by clay soils and this, in combination with a temperate climate, provides good conditions for humification of material added to the soil. Large areas of productive land also have a humus content above 3.4% soil organic matter (SOM) or 2% soil organic carbon (SOC), which in Sweden is seen as a breakpoint above which an increase in SOC can no longer be expected to increase crop yields [1].

Conditions for removing straw for uses other than feed and bedding are therefore relatively good. Considering the low humification factor and limited effect of straw incorporation on SOC reported in Swedish long-term trials [2, 3], there are many ways in which removal of straw from the field could be compensated for by other management measures for carbon sequestration.

2 METHODS

The straw potential was calculated for all Swedish counties at two levels: the theoretical amount available in the field for harvest and the amount remaining after deducting straw used in animal husbandry. The calculations were based on the cereal crop area as an average for the period 2011-2015 based on statistics [4-8]. The amount of straw available for collection from the field was calculated by multiplying the annual grain yield from Statistics Sweden by a factor for straw/grain ratio from Nilsson & Bernesson (2009) [9], assuming a stubble height of 20 cm.

To deduct the straw used in animal husbandry, assumptions from Mattsson (2006) [10] were used regarding the type and amount of straw (winter or/and spring cereal straw) used for different types of animals. To obtain total consumption of straw in each Swedish county, the quantity per animal was multiplied by the number of animals of each type per county.

A calculation was made for the Swedish demonstration case to supply 80,000 tonnes of winter wheat straw annually to the ethanol plant Lantmännen Agroetanol in Norrköping. The sustainability in removing straw from the case study area of Norrköping and surrounding counties was evaluated from a soil fertility aspect using the model Odlingsperspektiv [11]. This model estimates the sustainability of a cropping system regarding soil fertility and yield levels based on humus content, climate and soil type. The model is validated by e.g. data from Swedish long-term field trials and is regularly updated in cooperation with scientists at the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU).

A six-year crop rotation, typical for arable farms in the selected areas [12], was used as the base in the calculations for Norrköping and surrounding counties as well as for the county of Skåne in the south of Sweden (Table 1). Yield levels from Jordbruksverket (2016) [13] and average soil humus estimates from Naturvårdsverket (2010) [1] were used in each county. It was assumed that 40% of the total aboveground crop residue biomass (straw and chaff) was left in the field at straw harvest. The crop rotations were evaluated for two scenarios:

1) Base scenario, in which 80,000 tonnes of straw were collected in the counties Östergötland, Södermanland and Örebro. It was assumed that 100% of the sustainable winter wheat straw on crop farms was available for ethanol production, and that the amount of straw used for feed and bedding in animal production was covered by cereal production on animal farms. A criterion was that soil humus content should remain above 3.5% throughout a 50-year period, to maintain yield levels.

2) Skåne scenario, in which the 80,000 tonnes of straw were collected from another part of Sweden, in this case the county of Skåne.

It was assumed that 70% of the winter wheat straw resources (before deduction for animal husbandry) in the county of Östergötland was cultivated on arable farms. Corresponding values were 80% for Södermanland and Örebro counties and 85% for the county of Skåne.

Table I: Crop rotations (6 year) [12] and crop yields (kg/ha) [13] used for modelling straw removal in the surrounding counties Östergötland, Södermanland and Örebro and Skåne in the south of Sweden. (Ba=Barley, Oa=Oats, WW=Winter wheat, WR= Winter rape, SB= Sugar beets)

Crop rotation and yield (kg/ha)						
Östergötland						
Crops	Ba	Oa	WW	WR	WW	WW
Yield	4900	3800	6610	3300	6610	6610
Södermanland						
Crops	Ba	Oa	WW	WR	WW	WW
Yield	4300	3800	5530	3000	5530	5530
Örebro						
Crops	Ba	Oa	WW	WR	WW	WW
Yield	4616	4497	5930	1939	5930	5930
Skåne						
Crops	Ba	WW	WW	WR	WW	SB
Yield	5764	7560	7560	3978	7560	60000

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Straw potential in Sweden

For Sweden the calculated net potential of winter wheat straw available in counties with surplus of straw for collection was approx. 900,000 tonnes per year (Table 2).

Table II: Estimated available winter wheat straw resources in Sweden (tonnes straw/year) at 18% moisture content, after deduction of straw used for feed and bedding in animal husbandry

County	Straw amounts (tonnes/yr)
Stockholm	9.200
Uppsala	78.900
Södermanland	57.000
Östergötland	168.600
Kalmar	20.200
Gotland	17.400
Blekinge	2.900
Skåne	360.800
Halland	8.600
Västra Götaland	120.900
Örebro	26.000
Västmanland	30.900
Total Sweden counties with surplus	901.300

Furthermore, some counties, in particular in the north of Sweden, have a deficit of straw when considering the use in animal production. In total the deficit was estimated to 65,000 tonnes per year. The extent to which straw is transported between areas of surplus and areas with deficit is unknown, and needs to be further investigated.

3.2 Sustainable straw potential

An assessment of sustainable straw supply was made for the demonstration case of 80,000 tonnes annually to Lantmännen Agroetanol plant in Norrköping. The analysis of how much straw that could be removed without decrease in soil fertility, i.e. no negative effects on yield level in a 50- year perspective showed that soils in the counties in question generally have a high soil organic matter content. For the base scenario, using the average soil humus content per county in calculations gave a possible outtake of 230,000 tonnes of winter wheat straw from the three counties around Norrköping (Table 3).

Applying an average soil humus content to a large area will probably overestimate possible straw outtake of arable land in the counties in question generally has a high organic content. Since the content of organic material varies between different farms and fields, there will be areas in the counties from which it is only appropriate to collect small amounts of straw.

Table III: Amount of winter wheat straw (tonnes) available annually for removal without affecting yield levels in a 50-year perspective according to the model Odlingsperspektiv version 3.06 [6]. Estimated straw resource (18% moisture content) as percentage and amount (tonnes) produced on arable farms, and percentage and amount (tonnes) that can be removed without a risk of yield reduction according to calculations. (+) indicates scope for removing also other straw types than winter wheat straw.

	Total straw resources (tonnes ¹)	Resources at arable farms (tonnes)	Amount that can be removed (% ²)	(tonnes)
Östergötland	196,465	137,525	100(+)	137,525
Södermanland	75,538	60,430	100	60,430
Örebro	39,037	31,230	100(+)	31,230
Skåne	435,732	348,585	0	0

¹Amount of straw from straw/grain ratios, kg ww (18% moisture content).

²% of straw resources at arable farms.

For the Skåne scenario the model result indicated that, based on average soil humus content, it was not possible to remove any straw in the county of Skåne. This can be explained by the low average soil humus content of 3.0%, which was below the humus limit of 3.5% in a 50-year perspective, resulted in any straw removal may lead to a reduction in soil fertility and yield. However, humus-building management factors such as using cover and catch crops or ley as well as adding manure could enable removal of winter wheat straw without affecting soil humus content.

The model is primarily designed for comparing long-term trends between different management systems, rather than determining exact outtake levels. For example, previous cropping history, which will affect the long-term SOC equilibrium, is not included. Furthermore, other positive effects of straw incorporation, such as structural improvement and nutrient recycling, are not considered.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Regarding straw potential it is possible to supply the Swedish demonstration case in Norrköping with 80,000 tonnes of winter wheat straw. In the surrounding regions, as much as 230,000 tonnes could be available after taking account of any limitations regarding soil fertility aspects and the straw needed for animal production.

Conditions for taking out straw for energy production hence is relatively good. However, as humus content vary between fields, also in the same area, before actual outtake every field must be looked at individually to avoid negative effects on soil fertility.

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6 LOGO SPACE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 727961.